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LINGUISTIC AND PRAGMATIC ASPECTS OF THE NEWSPAPER TEXTS ON THE EXAMPLES OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article investigates linguistic and pragmatic aspects that are used in media discourse especially newspaper texts. It presents a comparative analysis of the linguistic and pragmatic features of newspaper texts in English and Uzbek languages, focusing on their similarities and differences. Linguistic analysis focuses on lexical choices and syntactic features of newspaper texts. While from pragmatic point of view, the study examines how newspaper texts employ various pragmatic strategies to achieve communicative goals. This study offers a comprehensive understanding of the similarities and differences in the construction and interpretation of news across languages*

Key words: *newspaper style, linguistic aspect, pragmatic aspect, implicature, speech acts theory.*

Introduction

Newspapers play important role in disseminating information, sharing public opinion, and reflecting social values. According to Bell(1991) newspapers are considered to be “language forming institutions”. As the primary function, newspapers created not the news, but the readers. Through the language used in newspapers, people get information and at the same time it has the power of influencing and persuading readers. Richardson(2007) claims that the language of newspapers can ‘do’ things in society. Newspapers appear in three formats: the broadsheet, the middle-range tabloids and tabloids, and main distinction between them being in size, style and news content (Reah, 2002).Newspaper texts are written in the style which varies from language to language. Kukharenko(1986)notes that the newspaper style refers only to those texts that can only be found in newspapers and cannot be found in other printed publications, such as magazines, posters, booklets, etc. According to Galperin English newspaper style has following basic features: *brief news items, advertisements and announcements, the headline and the editorial.* Whereas Uzbek newspapers are written in publicistic style which comprises the style of articles, newspapers and language of advertisements. The linguistic and pragmatic aspects of the newspaper texts have been a subject of research in many language contexts. Understanding linguistic aspects of newspaper texts involves analyzing the language used, including lexical choices, syntactic patterns, and rhetorical devices employed to convey information effectively. From the linguistic perspective, lexical,

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syntactical and discourse features play important role in organizing media texts. Van Dijk (1988) highlights the use of headlines, and subheadings as key features to facilitate text comprehension. Bell (2006) emphasizes the significance of specialized vocabulary, terminologies and neologisms used in newspapers. Pragmatics involves the study of all the conditions for the use of linguistic signs by mankind (Safarov, 2008). It includes the study of how language used in context, taking into account the intentions of the writers, implicatures, and socio-cultural norms.

Literature Review

Multiple research have been conducted to investigate linguistic and pragmatic features of newspaper texts in different languages. “A Corpus-based Stylistic Study of Newspaper English (1989) was written by E. Jeffries, which was based on a corpus of 2400 clauses taken from British national newspapers and stored in a computer database with grammatical features. Furthermore, Jasim Al-Saedi and Jabeer (2020) analyzed pragmatic aspects that are used in media discourse especially newspaper headlines in Iraqi official newspaper. Moreover, Schuster (2004) in his work analyzed newspaper articles from five different British newspapers. Another researcher M. Timucin (2010) published an article on “Different Language Styles in Newspaper- An Investigative Framework” in which he focused on linguistic devices like “core and non-core vocabulary” and “modality”. Basenko and Radchenko (2020) published an article on “Pragmalinguistic analysis of Newspaper headlines” based on the material of English newspaper “The Guardian”. From Uzbek researchers D. Teshabaeva published an article on “Linguopragmatic aspect of text in media”, in which linguopragmatic aspects of media texts are discussed.

Research Method

This research was carried out by means of comparative analysis of Uzbek and English newspaper languages from linguistic and pragmatic point of view. The study involved the following methodological steps:

1. Data Collection. The newspapers from both languages were collected. “The Guardian”, “The Times” from English newspapers and “Jamiyat”, “Khalq Sozi”, “Mahalla” from Uzbek newspapers.
2. Linguistic analysis. Comprehensive linguistic analysis of the selected newspaper texts was conducted. This analysis encompassed various levels of languages, including lexical choice, sentence structure, and morphology.
3. Pragmatic analysis. To investigate the pragmatic aspects of the newspaper texts, a pragmatic framework which includes politeness strategies, implicatures and speech acts were employed.

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By following this research methodology, this article is aimed to provide a comprehensive and comparative analysis of the linguistic and pragmatic aspects of the newspaper texts in Uzbek and English languages, focusing on their similarities and differences.

Data Analysis

1. Linguistic aspects of the newspaper texts

1.1. Lexical choice

The choice of vocabulary and lexical items in Uzbek and English languages can differ due to differences in language structure, cultural context and stylistic conventions. Uzbek newspaper texts contain loanwords from other languages, such as Russian, English, Arabic and Persian. For example, “*Biznes*”, “*Internet*”, “*Kredit*” borrowed from English, “*Reklama*”, “*Stadion*” borrowed from Russian, “*Safar*”, “*Darvoza*” borrowed from Persian language. English newspaper texts include jargon and technical terms specific to various fields such as politics, economics, science, sports and entertainment. For instance, “*Caucus*”- a meeting of members of political party to select candidates, “*Bull Market*”- a period of rising stock prices in financial markets, “*Genome*”- the complete set of genes or genetic material present in an organism. Besides that, Uzbek newspaper texts tend to utilize formal and standard vocabulary, avoiding colloquial or regional expressions. Formal language is also used in English newspaper texts, but they also can incorporate idiomatic expressions, and colloquialisms:

“...*Davlatimiz rahbari bu imkoniyatlardan oqilona foydalanib, hududlarda loyihalarni va ish o‘rinlarini ko‘paytirish kerakligini ta’kidladi. Yig‘ilishda muhokama qilingan masalalar yuzasidan mutasaddilar axborot berdi.*” (Khalq sozi, 2024)

“.....*It took Carolyn Fellwock and Charlie Watson only 11 months to tie the knot after meeting on Yahoo Personals-and three years more to call it quits*(The Times, 2008)

The idiom “to tie the knot” means to get married

The idiom “to call it quits” means to end something

1.2. Sentence structure

There are several differences between syntactic structures used in Uzbek and English newspaper texts. Firstly, Uzbek language follows *subject+object+verb(SOV)* word order:

“... *O‘zbekiston tashqi siyosati faollashgan davrga qadam qo‘ydi*”. (Khalq Sozi, 2024)

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English follows *subject+verb+object(SVO)* word order:

“...UK rejects EU free movement for young people offer” (*The Times*,2024)

Moreover, Uzbek newspaper texts use postpositional phrases to demonstrate relationship between nouns and other elements in the sentence:

“.....Davlat tomonidan yangi siyosat amalga oshirildi” (*Jamiyat*,2023)

English newspaper texts mostly employ relative clauses to provide additional information about a noun or a noun phrase:

“...Details of the survey-which involved inputs from 187 scientists-will be revealed at ESCMID congress next weekend” (*The Guardian*,2024)

1.3. Morphology

Morphological features of a language include inflectional and derivational processes, word formation, and grammatical categories. Uzbek is an agglutinative language, that consist of multiple morphemes that are attached together. For example, “*yurtimizda*” here one word consists of 3 morphemes: “*yurt*”-homeland, “*yurtimiz*”-our homeland, “*yurtimizda*”-in our homeland. On the other hand, English is an isolating language, where words are formed by combining independent morphemes. For instance, “*In our country*” - morphemes are separated here. Furthermore, in both languages passive voice construction is frequently used . For example:

“.....Mazkur qonunda ko‘chmas mulklarga nisbatan huquqlar e’tirof etilishi belgilandi” (*Khalq Sozi*,2024)

“.....The Senate is expected to vote on the bill next week” (*The Guardian*,2024)

2. Pragmatic aspects of newspaper texts

2.1. Politeness strategies

The use of politeness markers differs in both languages. Uzbek newspaper texts employ honorific language and polite forms to show respect and maintain social status. This includes appropriate forms of address or honorific title when referring to individuals of higher social status or authority. For example, “ *Muhtaram Prezidentimiz*” when addressing to the head of government. Moreover, instead of directly criticizing a person or their actions, Uzbek newspaper texts may use phrases like “*Bir qancha muammolar mavjud*”, “*E’tibor qaratilishi kerak*”. Besides that, English newspaper texts often prioritize objective reporting, presenting facts and events in a neutral manner, while Uzbek newspapers exhibit a more subjective reporting style, with the inclusion of personal opinions, emotions and comments by the journalist:

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“.....According to official sources, the government has denied the allegations of corruption” (The Times,2024)

“.....Bugun bemalol ayta olamiz:nafaqat viloyat markazi, balki eng chekka tumanlargacha sanoat kirib bordi” (Khalq Sozi,2024)

2.2. Implicature

The term “ implicature” accounts for what a speaker can imply, suggest or mean, as distinct from what the speaker literally says(Grice, 1975). Levinson(1983) states that the notion of implicature provides some explicit account of how it is possible to mean more than what is literally expressed in the conventional sense of the linguistic expression uttered. The implicatures in Uzbek newspaper texts focus on government policies, healthcare and education:

“...Endilikda Prezidentimizning topshiriqlari asosida mahalliy ijro hokimiyati organlari faoliyatini tartibga soluvchi qonun loyihasi ishlab chiqariladi” (Mahalla,2021)

English newspapers cover broader themes that can be found in newspapers worldwide, including politics, company operations, and societal matters:

“.....Scientists discover promising breakthrough in cancer research” (Guardian,2024)

2.3. Speech Acts

Speech acts are considered as one of the most important pragmatic aspect. Searle (1975) discusses how the use of speech acts, such as assertions, directives contribute to the news reporting. He classified 5 categories of soeech acts. They are: declarations, assertives, expressives, directives, and commissives.

Assertives	The speaker commits to the truth of what is asserted	Xalqimiz demokratiyaga qaramay, mustaqillikni olishga qaror qildi	The government announced new economic reforms to stimulate job creation
Directives	The speaker makes an attempt to get the subject to do something by expressing his/her wish	Ovoz berish jarayoni 15-oktabrda amalga oshiriladi. To'g'ri ovoz berishni unutmang	Please submit your applications by Friday to be consideredfor the scholarship

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Commissive	The speaker commits to take an action in future	Kelgusidagi kengashda sizning fikrlaringiz inobatga olinishi mumkin	We promise to deliver the project on time and within the allocated budget
Expressives	The speaker expresses a variety of psychological states	Biz xalqimizning qo'lida turar joyi uchun hamkorlarimizga minnatdorlik bildiramiz	Our heartfelt thanks to the volunteers who tirelessly worked to assist those affected by the natural disaster
Declarations	The speaker brings about a change in the world via words	Hukumat investitsiyalar yo'lida to'liq yondashiladigan qonunlarni takomillashtirishga qaror qildi	The company announced its intention to expand its operations in to new markets within the next year

Results

Having conducted the research, it is possible to draw following conclusions:

1. Regarding linguistic aspects, both English and Uzbek languages consist of high degree of lexical richness and variation. However, Uzbek language tend to use more loanwords compared to English language. Whereas, English language tend to employ a wider range of technical terms and jargons.

2. Regarding syntactic structures, English newspaper texts demonstrated a preference for complex sentence structures. In contrast, in Uzbek newspaper texts simple sentence structures are used most.

3. In terms of pragmatic aspects, English newspaper texts aimed to provide objective information with informative and descriptive strategies. Whereas, Uzbek newspaper texts emphasize more on politeness strategies. Moreover, Uzbek language

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has a complex system of honorifics that can be used to convey respect and politeness. English, on the other hand, has a less elaborate system of formal language

Conclusion

To conclude, newspapers play a significant role in the life of society as a source of information. They provide a comprehensive overview of current events allowing readers to stay informed about the world around them. The language of the newspaper has a certain specific characters that distinguish it from the language of fiction and scientific literature, from oral speech. This is the result of selection of suitable language expressive means. Language and pragmatic features in newspapers reflect and shape cultural, political and ideological dimensions. The study of linguistic and pragmatic aspects of newspaper texts provides valuable insights into the dynamics of news communication.

References:

1. Basenko G,V; Radchenko G.I(2020) Pragmalinguistic analysis of newspaper headlines(Based on the material of the English newspaper “The Guardian”)
2. Bell,A (1991). ‘Stylin’ the news audience design’ in the Language of the News Media. Oxford:Blackwell
3. Grice,P.(1975). Logic and Conversation. New York:Academic Press
4. Jeffries, E(1989).A Corpus-based Stylistic study of Newspaper English
5. Kukhareno(1986) V.A.Practical course of stylistics of the English language. Moscow.
6. Levinson S. (1983). Pragmatics.Cambridge University Press
7. Reah D.(2002). The language of newspapers. London:Routledge
8. Richardson J (2007). Analysing Newspapers: An approach from critical discourse analysis. New York:Palgrave Macmillan
9. Saeedi and Jabeer(2020). A pragmatic study of newspaper headlines in media discourse: Iraq as a case study
10. Safarov, Sh (2008). Pragmalingvistika. Toshkent
11. Schuster(2004). Linguistic analysis of British newspaper texts
12. Searle,J.(1975). Syntax and Semantics. Academic Press
13. Teshabaeva, D(2021). Linguopragmatic aspect of text in media
14. Timucin, M (2010). Different Language Styles in Newspaper-An Investigative Framework
15. Van Dijk, T.A (1988). News as discourse. Hillsdale, US:Lawrence Elbaum Associates Inc.
16. “Jamiyat”, Toshkent, 2023.
17. “Khalq Sozi”, “Sharq” nashriyot-manba aksiyadorlik kompaniyasi,2024.
18. “Mahalla”, Toshkent, 2021.
19. “The Times”, New York, 2008, 2024.
20. “The Guardian”, Manchester, 2024.